

Influence of Solvent Interaction on the Absorption Spectra of Some Phenol Betaines. Part II

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Phenol betaines derived from styryl 2-quinoline have been prepared and their absorption spectra have been recorded. They show a characteristic intramolecular charge-transfer absorption band in the visible region which is not present in the parent conjugate acid. This band undergoes a blue shift in the medium of hydroxylic solvents which is attributed to hydrogen bonding. The shifting of this band in the polar solvents is in keeping with the dipolar nature of these betaines.

In a previous communication¹, synthesis and the absorption spectra of phenol betaines derived from hydroxy-4-stilbazole have been described¹. This paper deals with the synthesis and effect of solvent interaction on the absorption spectra of phenol betaines derived from hydroxystyryl-2-quinoline. The preparation of various styryl-2-quinolines and their quaternary salts has been described by a number of workers²⁻⁸.

These hydroxystyryl-2-quinolines were obtained as yellow solids by heating equimolecular quantities of quinaldine with hydroxybenzaldehydes at 160°–170° in presence of acetic anhydride. The methiodides of these compounds were prepared in the usual way and were found to be identical with the methiodides of hydroxystyryl-2-quinolines reported by Schneider and Pothman⁷. These quaternary salts on treatment with aqueous alkali gave deep orange or red coloured solutions due to the formation of the betaines, which were isolated by extraction with chloroform. The betaines I, II and III were found to be stable due to the existence of the quinonoid structure. In the case of betaine V such canonical forms are not possible, which accounts for its instability. The betaine IV was found to be stable only in solution and decomposes on removing the solvent.

The betaines I, II, III and IV gave purple or blue colour in chloroform and red colour in ethanol. The absorption maxima of betaines and quaternary salts are recorded in the Tables I and II.

For the sake of comparison with original methiodides, their absorption maxima were also recorded at different pH and thus the absorption maxima of betaines IV and V could also be studied.

TABLE I

Absorption maxima of betaines in the visible region

S.No.	Betaines	Solvents			
		Ethanol		Chloroform	
		λ_{max}	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{max}	$\log \epsilon$
1.	N-methyl 2'-hydroxystyryl	550 $m\mu$	4.20	440 $m\mu$	3.61
	2-quinolinium hydroxide anhydro salt	—	—	570 $m\mu$	4.65
2.	N-methyl 4'-hydroxystyryl	420 $m\mu$	4.26	440 $m\mu$	3.85
	2-quinolinium hydroxide anhydro salt	550 $m\mu$	4.45	575 $m\mu$	4.72
3.	N-methyl 4'-hydroxy 3'-methoxy styryl	430 $m\mu$	4.14	450 $m\mu$	3.92
	2-quinolinium hydroxide anhydro salt	580 $m\mu$	4.41	590 $m\mu$	4.61
4.	N-methyl 3'4'-dihydroxystyryl	430 $m\mu$	—	450 $m\mu$	—
	2-quinolinium hydroxide anhydro salt	570 $m\mu$	—	591 $m\mu$	—

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of hydroxystyryl 2-quinolines: 0.02 mol of the appropriate hydroxybenzaldehyde viz., salicylaldehyde, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, vanillin and protocatechuic aldehyde was boiled under reflux with 0.02 mol of quinaldine in presence of 10 ml of acetic anhydride on an oil bath at 160°–170° for a period ranging from 4 to 12 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was boiled with 20 ml of *N*/2 hydrochloric acid. The acid solution

was then neutralised with ammonia and the yellow solid of hydroxystyryl 2-quinoline was filtered, and washed with hot water 3 to 4 times to remove unreacted aldehyde. The solid was crystallised from ethanol or benzene containing small amount of activated charcoal.

TABLE 2

S. No.	The quaternary iodide of	Acidic Ethanol		Alkaline Ethanol		D.M.F.	
		λ_{\max} .	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{\max} .	$\log \epsilon$	λ_{\max} .	$\log \epsilon$
1.	I	213 $m\mu$	4.57	214 $m\mu$	4.72	267 $m\mu$	4.13
		242 $m\mu$	4.50	285 $m\mu$	4.02	395 $m\mu$	3.52
		285 $m\mu$	3.97	550 $m\mu$	4.48	610 $m\mu$	3.85
		405 $m\mu$	4.46				
2.	II	216 $m\mu$	4.76	215 $m\mu$	4.71	319 $m\mu$	3.62
		261 $m\mu$	4.47	422 $m\mu$	3.94	430 $m\mu$	3.69
		425 $m\mu$	4.36	560 $m\mu$	4.82	570 $m\mu$	4.60
3. •	III	217 $m\mu$	4.38	219 $m\mu$	4.88	267 $m\mu$	4.16
		254 $m\mu$	4.05	335 $m\mu$	3.65	445 $m\mu$	3.77
		315 $m\mu$	3.95	405 $m\mu$	3.88	350 $m\mu$	4.10
		445-50 $m\mu$	4.35	590 $m\mu$	4.77	595 $m\mu$	4.50
4.	IV	216 $m\mu$	4.45	215 $m\mu$	4.51	267 $m\mu$	3.92
		316 $m\mu$	3.97	430 $m\mu$	3.87	445 $m\mu$	3.82
		445 $m\mu$	4.47	570 $m\mu$	4.78	590 $m\mu$	4.75
5.	V	214 $m\mu$	4.45	216 $m\mu$	4.34	267 $m\mu$	4.58
		266 $m\mu$	3.98	298 $m\mu$	3.85	400-5 $m\mu$	4.02
		280 $m\mu$	3.99	370 $m\mu$	3.69		
		410 $m\mu$	4.48	440 $m\mu$	4.09		

Preparation of methiodides of hydroxystyryl 2-quinolines : These compounds were prepared according to the method of Saxena and Stafford⁹ using absolute alcohol in place of acetone and crystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of phenol betaines : These were prepared from respective quaternary salts by the method described by Saxena and Stafford⁹.

The melting points and analyses of various compounds prepared are given in the Table III.

DISCUSSION

A study of the absorption spectra of the betaines I, II, III and IV shows that like merocyanines, there is a bathochromic shift in the absorption maxima (Table I) in the longer wavelength by using a solvent of low dielectric constant, chloroform ($D = 4.9$) in place of

TABLE 3

S. No.	Compound	Time of Reflux	Colour	M.P.	Yield	Analysis %
1.	2'-hydroxystyryl-2-quinoline (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON)	10 hr	yellow	206°	1.7 gm	Found C, 82.05; H, 5.03 Reqd. C, 82.59; H, 5.26
	methiodide of above (C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ONI)	1½ hr	yellow turns brown	212°	—	Found I, 32.18 Reqd. I, 32.65
	picrate of methiodide (C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₄)	—	red	172°	—	Found N, 11.03 Reqd. N, 11.42
	Betaine I	—	shining light black	185°	—	m.p. of picrate mixed m.p. with above undepress- ed.
2.	3'-hydroxystyryl 2-quinoline (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON)	12 hr	yellow	194°	1.8 gm	Found C, 81.96; H, 5.06 Reqd. C, 82.59; H, 5.26
	methiodide of above (C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ONI)	1 hr	dirty yellow	230° reported 224°	—	Found I, 32.21 Reqd. I, 32.66
	picrate of methiodide (C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₄)	—	yellow	211-13°	—	Found N, 10.95 Reqd. N, 11.41
3.	3'-hydroxystyryl 2-quinoline (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ON)	9 hr	yellow	257°	—	Found C, 82.12 H, 5.01 Reqd. C, 82.59 H, 5.26
	methiodide of above (C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N)	1 hr	yellow brown needles	234° reported 231°	—	Found I, 32.22 Reqd. I, 32.66
	picrate of methiodide (C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₄)	—	golden yellow	218°	—	Found N, 11.02 Reqd. N, 11.41
	Betaine II	—	brown black	208°	—	m.p. 218° of pic-

TABLE III—Contd.

S.No.	Compound	Time of Reflux	Colour	M.P.	Yield	Analysis %
				210° reported		erate.
4.	1'-hydroxy-3'-methoxystyryl-2-quinoline (C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N)	4½ hr	bright yellow	180°	—	Found C, 77.42 H, 5.13 Reqd. C, 77.97 H, 5.41
	methiodide of above (C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₁)	2 hr	red	254°	—	Found I, 29.83 Reqd. I, 30.31
	picrate of methiodide (C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₉ N ₄)	—	red	232°	—	Found N, 10.23 Reqd. N, 10.75
	Betaine III	—	brown black	142°	—	m.p. 231° of picrate.
5.	3',4'-dihydroxystyryl-2-quinoline (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₂ N)	5 hr	yellow changing brown	244°	—	Found C, 77.03; H, 4.49 Reqd. C, 77.56; H, 4.94
	methiodide of above (C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₁)	2 hr	orange	257-59°	—	Found I, 31.35 Reqd. I, 31.01
	picrate of methiodide (C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₉ N ₄)	—	red	189°	—	Found N, 10.73 Reqd. N, 11.04

a solvent of high dielectric constant, ethanol ($D = 24.3$). The hypsochromic shift in ethanol is attributed to the hydrogen bonding of ethanol molecules with those of betaine.

In the case of the spectra of the methiodides in acidic ethanol (Table II), the characteristic absorption maxima in the longer wavelength of the visible region is not present, however in alkaline ethanol, this absorption maxima in the longer wavelength of the visible region appears which indicates the formation of betaines from the methiodides. But in D.M.F., acting as a solvent ($D = 26.6$), a further red shift is observed in the absorption maxima of the methiodides as compared to that in alkaline ethanol. This is contrary to the expected effect of the polar solvent interaction on the betaines. The bathochromic shifting of this band may be ascribed to a prior formation of the betaine from methiodide by the basic action of D.M.F. (as in alkaline ethanol) and then betaines molecules are involved in the formation of CT complex with D.M.F molecules, as indicated by the high extinction values of the band in the longer wavelength.

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R E F E R E N C E

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